

Study of azoester mesogenic homologous series : *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-*o*-methyl phenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes

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Mesogenic homologous series : *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxybenzoyloxy)-*o*-methyl phenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes are synthesized to understand the effects of structural variation on mesogenic characteristics. All the members of the homologous series exhibit nematogenic character enantiotropically except first and second homologues, which shows monotropic nematic character. Present series is predominantly nematogenic and partly smectogenic with its mesomorphic range from 39 to 76°C. Thermal stabilities and liquid crystal properties are compared with other structurally identical homologous series.

Homologous series¹ with -COO- and -N=N- central bridges have been synthesized. In continuation of our work, present work is planned to understand the relation between mesogenic characteristics and structural variation of the molecules.

Experimental

p-Hydroxy-*o*-methylphenylazo-*p*-chlorobenzene was prepared from *p*-chloroaniline and *m*-cresol by routine diazotization process¹.

p-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyl chlorides are coupled with *p*-hydroxy-*o*-methyl phenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes by usual method¹ and as given in the following paper.

Transition temperatures are observed through Laborlux polarizing microscope with heating stage and recorded in Table 1. Analytical data are given in Table 2.

Results and discussion

p-Hydroxy-*o*-methylphenylazo-*p*-chlorobenzene is a non-liquid crystalline substance. However, addition of phenyl ring linked through -COO- central bridge and *para* substituted *n*-alkoxy left terminal, increases the length and aromaticity of the molecule. Increased length and aromaticity of molecules increases polarity, polarizability and length to breadth ratio, causing induction of liquid crystallinity in the molecules. Thus added linking units with azodye though being non-liquid crystal, produces first and second homologues as monotropic nematic. Third to eighth homo-

No. of carbon atoms in <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Transition temperatures in °C		
	Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1	–	(124.0)	170.0
2	–	(146.0)	180.0
3	–	87.0	163.0
4	–	118.0	157.0
5	–	113.0	155.0
6	–	94.0	149.0
7	–	91.0	147.0
8	–	87.0	141.0
10	81.0	87.0	135.0
12	77.0	112.0	130.0
14	86.0	115.0	130.0
16	90.0	118.0	129.0

logues are enantiotropic nematic²; tenth, twelfth, fourteenth and sixteenth homologues of the series are poly mesomorphic³, with exhibition of smectic and nematic mesophase within definite range of temperature enantiotropically.

Thus series is predominantly nematogenic and partly smectogenic. Nematic mesophase has threaded texture while smectic mesophase is focal conic fan shaped with A or C variety as judged directly from the field of view of microscope. Thermal stabilities of the series (I) under present discussion is compared with other structurally similar series (A)¹ and (B)².

Table 2. Analytical and spectral data

Sr. no.	R = <i>n</i> -Alkyl chain	Molecular formula	Calculated %			Observed %		
			C	H	N	C	H	N
1.	Methyl	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	66.23	4.47	7.36	65.95	4.52	7.48
2.	Ethyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	66.92	4.82	7.10	67.08	4.69	6.98
3.	Propyl	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	67.56	5.14	6.85	67.21	5.29	6.91
4.	Butyl	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	68.17	5.44	6.63	68.09	5.19	6.59
5.	Pentyl	C ₂₅ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	68.73	5.73	6.41	68.66	5.61	6.34
6.	Hexyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	69.26	5.99	6.22	68.92	5.81	6.09
7.	Heptyl	C ₂₇ H ₂₉ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	69.75	6.24	6.03	69.58	6.48	5.96
8.	Octyl	C ₂₈ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	70.22	6.48	5.85	70.33	6.56	5.81
9.	Decyl	C ₃₀ H ₃₅ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	71.08	6.91	5.53	72.03	6.91	5.42
10.	Dodecyl	C ₃₂ H ₃₉ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	71.84	7.30	5.24	72.03	7.42	5.31
11.	Tetradecyl	C ₃₄ H ₄₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	72.53	7.64	4.98	72.36	7.34	4.83
12.	Hexadecyl	C ₃₆ H ₄₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	73.16	7.96	4.74	72.98	7.88	4.78
	Homologue	IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)						
	Pentyl	2935, 2854, 1429 cm ⁻¹ → alkyl group 1683, 1255, 1218 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- group 1396 cm ⁻¹ → -N=N- group 1051 cm ⁻¹ → -O- group 844 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -sub. benzene 549 cm ⁻¹ → C-Cl aromatic IR conforms above structure						
	Heptyl	2933, 2850 cm ⁻¹ → alkyl group 1672, 1255, 1170 cm ⁻¹ → -COO- group 1394 cm ⁻¹ → -N=N- group 1062 cm ⁻¹ → -O- group 844 cm ⁻¹ → <i>p</i> -sub. benzene 549 cm ⁻¹ → C-Cl aromatic IR conforms above structure						

(1) *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-*o*-methylphenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes

(A) *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)phenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes

(B) *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-*m*-methylphenylazo-*p''*-chlorobenzenes

The varied display of molecular forces which in their peculiar combination affect the liquid crystal property has been significantly used for proper understanding and evaluation of the phenomenon. Polarity, polarizability, length to breadth ratio, rigidity and linearity of molecule, steric hindrance caused by laterally substituted groups to the molecule, planar nature, pi electron density etc. have been considered to be sufficiently important besides several other factors in deciding liquid crystal characteristics of the molecule.

Smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic thermal stabilities

Table 3. Relative thermal stabilities in °C

Series →	(I)	(A)	(B)
Smectic-Nematic or	108.0	148.7	106.6
Smectic-Isotropic	(C ₁₀ -C ₁₆)	(C ₆ -C ₁₆)	(C ₁₂ -C ₁₆)
Commencement of smectic mesophase	C ₁₀	C ₆	C ₁₂
Nematic-Isotropic or	142.16	217.6	170.0
Isotropic-Nematic	(C ₁ -C ₁₆)	(C ₁ -C ₁₀)	(C ₁ -C ₁₀)
Commencement of nematic mesophase	C ₁	C ₁	C ₁

are recorded in Table 3. Smectic thermal stability of title homologous series (I) and (B) are almost equal but less than series (A). Equality of thermal stabilities of series (I) and (B) is very well understood with respect to same -CH₃ group at *ortho* or *meta* position identically attached at middle phenyl ring. Likewise higher value of smectic-nematic thermal stability for series (A) is also very well understood with respect to closer packing of molecules without any lateral substitution at middle phenyl ring. The nematic isotropic thermal stabilities of homologous series (A) is the highest and that of title homologous series (I) is the lowest. This variation is reflected in smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic thermal stability of series-I and series-B. Nematic property is indirectly favoured to the maximum extent in series (A) because of its linearity without lateral substitution favouring parallel orientations of the molecule even in the floating condition. In case of title homologous series (I) and series (B) factors pertaining to exhibition of liquid crystal property with reference to smectic mesophase is equally favourable irrespective of *ortho* or *meta* substitution of -CH₃ group. Commencement of smectic mesophase is de-

pendent upon the non-coplanarity of the molecule. This is reflected from Table 3.

Thus smectic and nematic group efficiency order derived with respect to lateral substitution is as under when left and right terminals, central bridges and aromaticity of molecules are unchanging part. Smectic : -H > (*ortho*) -CH₃ ≈ (*meta*) -CH₃, Nematic : -H > (*ortho*) -CH₃ > (*meta*) -CH₃.

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